

This presentation was selected by the Sc. Committee of the EU PVSEC 2025 for submission of a full paper to one of the EU PVSEC's collaborating peer-reviewed journals.

BRIDGING THE GAP: INSIGHTS INTO BACKTRACKING-ANGLE RELATED DISCREPANCIES BETWEEN ESTIMATES AND ACTUAL PERFORMANCE IN LARGE-SCALE PHOTOVOLTAIC PLANTS

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ABSTRACT: Energy yield overestimation in large-scale photovoltaic (PV) simulations is a recurring issue that affects the accuracy of performance predictions. Analysis of SCADA data from four single-axis PV plants in different regions revealed systematic deviations between simulated and measured tracker angles during backtracking periods, prompting an investigation into the role of the estimated tracking irradiation gain (TIG) in these discrepancies. These deviations seemed to be linked to empirical corrections implemented to mitigate shading caused by terrain unevenness, which introduces elevation differences between tracker rows. While these adjustments reduce shading losses, they also modify the trackers' optimal tilt, lowering incident irradiance and ultimately reducing energy yield. A reverse-engineering approach was used to derive an equivalent correction model, based on a theoretical reduction in the effective inter-row spacing. When implemented in simulation tools, this correction produced TIG values 7–10% lower than those predicted under ideal flat-terrain conditions, leading to annual energy yield overestimations of around 3%. The results underscore the importance of accounting for realistic tracking behavior in energy yield simulations to improve both technical accuracy and the financial predictability of PV projects.

Keywords: energy yield overestimation, tracking irradiation gain, backtracking, terrain unevenness effects, PV simulation.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the growth of installed PV capacity and the increasing relevance of solar energy have drawn attention to the persistent overestimation of expected energy yields in large-scale PV plants [1] [2]. Within these discrepancies between actual and simulated results, the tracking irradiation gain (TIG) emerges as a key performance indicator (KPI), as it directly influences the energy yield.

Reports and consultations received at the Instituto de Energía Solar (IES) of the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM) frequently indicate that the TIG observed in large commercial single-axis tracking PV plants is systematically lower than the values predicted by simulations performed during the project design phase for bankability purposes. TIG, defined as the relative increase in irradiation collected by single-axis tracking systems compared to horizontal (zero-tilt) configurations, plays a central role in energy yield modelling and is given by

$$\text{TIG}_{\tau}(\omega) = \frac{G_T(\omega) - G_T(0)}{G_T(0)}, \quad (1)$$

where $G_T(\omega)$ and $G_T(0)$ represent the solar irradiation accumulated during a period T on a plane tilted at angle ω and on a horizontal plane, respectively. It must be noted that a reduction in TIG does not affect the performance ratio (PR) or the availability indicators of the PV plants. For this reason, despite its relevance, this phenomenon has so far received little attention in the open literature.

This work investigates the causes of the lower-than-expected TIG through the analysis of four PV plants equipped with different tracker models installed on horizontal terrain. The study shows that terrain irregularities, often ignored in simulation models, produce small but systematic deviations in tracker alignment. These deviations require corrective adjustments in tracking operation to mitigate shading and the appearance of hot spots, but such adjustments come at the cost of reducing the amount of captured irradiance.

By focusing on TIG itself, this study aims to improve

the understanding of the gap between simulated and actual values of this KPI and to emphasize the need to incorporate these effects into future energy yield assessments, leading to more accurate and financially reliable PV project evaluations.

2 MODELLING THE TRACKING ANGLES

This work focuses on quantifying the impact of tracker positioning during backtracking periods on the TIG in utility-scale PV plants equipped with horizontal single-axis trackers. This configuration is projected to represent nearly 40% of the market share in utility solar PV installations by 2030 [3]. To that end, the geometric framework underlying the computation of tracker rotation angles is introduced, as implemented in SISIFO, a simulation software developed by IES-UPM. SISIFO was developed within the European projects PVCROPS [4], MASLOWATEN [5] and PVOP [6]. It supports the simulation of grid-connected and pumping PV systems, including features such as mutual shading modeling [7] [8], multiple tracking strategies [9], and bifacial operation on sloped terrain [10]. The models for irradiance distribution, decomposition, transposition, and spectral correction are detailed in [11] [12] [13].

The physical domain is modeled as a three-dimensional affine space $\mathcal{A}_0 \equiv (\mathbb{R}^3, \mathbb{R}^3, \phi)$, where $\phi: \mathcal{A}_0 \times \mathcal{A}_0 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^3$ denotes the vector difference, and the associated vector space $(\mathbb{R}^3, \|\cdot\|)$ is equipped with the standard Euclidean norm derived from the usual scalar product. The natural Euclidean distance $d_0: \mathcal{A}_0 \times \mathcal{A}_0 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is used to compute physical distances in this space.

A right-handed Cartesian coordinate system (x, y, z) is introduced, with origin $\mathcal{O} \in \mathcal{A}_0$ located on the rotation axis of a reference tracker, at a height H_0 above ground level. The x -axis points East–West, the y -axis points North–South, and the z -axis is aligned with the zenith direction.

Trackers are assumed to be arranged in equidistant,

parallel rows indexed by $n \in \mathbb{Z}$, where $n = 0$ corresponds to the reference tracker. Rows to the right (respectively, left) are indexed by consecutive positive (respectively, negative) integers.

The solar position is calculated using the standard solar position equations [11] and is characterized by two standard angles: the solar azimuth γ_S , defined as the angle between the projection of the Sun onto the horizontal plane and the geographic North (positive eastwards), and the solar zenith angle θ_S , defined as the angle between the Sun and the vertical direction.

Tracker rotation is described by its tilt angle ω , measured with respect to the horizontal plane, and its azimuth angle, corresponding to the orientation of the rotation axis. In typical utility-scale configurations, including the ones considered in this work, trackers are aligned along the North–South direction, corresponding to azimuth $\alpha = 0$.

To simplify the analysis, SISIFO adopts a two-dimensional geometric representation in which the working domain is defined as the vertical plane orthogonal to the tracker rotation axis. For North–South-aligned trackers, this plane is orthogonal to the local meridian and is modeled as an affine plane $\mathcal{A} \subset \mathcal{A}_0$, endowed with the Euclidean distance $d: \mathcal{A} \times \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ induced from d_0 . An affine frame $\mathcal{R} = \{\mathcal{O}; \mathcal{B}\}$ is fixed in \mathcal{A} , where \mathcal{B} is the standard orthonormal basis of \mathbb{R}^2 . Coordinates in this plane are denoted by (x, z) . Within this working plane, the projection of the Sun's position is represented by the point $P_S \equiv (x_S, z_S)$, where $x_S = \cos \gamma_S \sin \theta_S$ and $z_S = \sin \theta_S$.

For subsequent analysis, the Euclidean distance in \mathcal{A} is normalized so that the projected width of a tracker cross-section equals one unit. Specifically, if the projected endpoints of the n -th tracker cross-section in \mathcal{A} are denoted by $E_{1,n}$ and $E_{2,n}$, for every $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ it is imposed the following condition,

$$d(E_{1,n}, E_{2,n}) = 1. \quad (2)$$

As a result, trackers are assumed to be evenly spaced by a normalized distance L_{EW} (East–West spacing) between consecutive rotation axes.

Figure 1 shows a schematic of the model implemented where blue segments represent the cross-sections of the trackers on the working domain. The baseline corresponds to the intersection between the working plane and the ground, assumed to be a perfectly horizontal plane. Yellow segments indicate illuminated ground areas, and black segments correspond to shaded ground regions. The trace of the Sun's ray is shown as a dashed black line. These colour conventions will be maintained in all subsequent figures, unless explicitly stated otherwise.

Figure 1: Simplified layout of the model. Trackers are shown in blue, and the ground is a horizontal line at height $-H$, with sunlit (yellow) and shaded (black) regions. The sun path appears as a dashed black line. The colour code

employed for the notation corresponds to the colour of the respective elements it denotes.

2.1 Backtracking angles

In configurations with horizontal single-axis trackers, the rotation angle of each tracker is dynamically adjusted according to the position of the Sun. The ideal tracking condition corresponds to orienting the active surface of each generator such that the projection of the incident solar rays onto the working plane is orthogonal to the generator's cross-section. Equivalently, the normal vector to the tilted surface becomes collinear with the projection of the solar rays within this plane, thereby maximizing the irradiance collected by the active surface.

From simple trigonometric considerations, the corresponding ideal tracking angle ω_{ID} with respect to the horizontal is given by

$$\omega_{ID} = \text{atan} \frac{x_S}{z_S}. \quad (3)$$

However, this ideal configuration is not always feasible. At low solar altitudes, insufficient inter-row spacing may lead to one tracker row casting a shadow over the adjacent one, as schematically illustrated in **Figure 2**.

Figure 2: Schematic representation of the shadow cast between adjacent tracker rows at low solar altitudes, represented as red segments. The notation uses the same colour as the element it represents.

To avoid mutual shading between rows under these conditions, trackers are intentionally rotated away from the ideal direction, this strategy is known as backtracking.

To formalize the backtracking condition, the direction of sunlight projected onto the working domain $\mathcal{A} \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ is considered. Let

$$k_S = \frac{(x_S, z_S)}{\sqrt{x_S^2 + z_S^2}} \quad (4)$$

denote the unit vector indicating the solar ray direction in the working plane, and $\pi_z: \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ the projection onto the vertical axis, that is, for any point $(x, y, z) \in \mathbb{R}^3$, $\pi_z(x, y, z) = z$. Based on the vector in Equation (4), an oblique projection operator $\mathcal{T}_{k_S}: \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \mathcal{G}$ is defined, mapping each point $P \in \mathcal{A}$ to the intersection of the ray emitted from P in the direction of k_S with the horizontal line $\mathcal{G} = \{(x, -H) \in \mathcal{A} | x \in \mathbb{R}\}$, where $H = \left(H_0 + \min(\pi_z(E_{1,n}), \pi_z(E_{2,n})) \right) / d_0(E_{1,n}, E_{2,n})$ for any $n \in \mathbb{Z}$. That is,

$$\mathcal{T}_{k_S}(P) = (P + \lambda \cdot k_S) \cap \mathcal{G}, \quad (5)$$

for some $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$. Formally, backtracking is triggered when the distance between the points $\mathcal{T}_{k_S}(E_{2,n})$ and $E_{1,n}$ or between the points $\mathcal{T}_{k_S}(E_{1,n})$ and $E_{2,n}$ exceeds the normalized inter-row spacing L_{EW} , for any $n \in \mathbb{Z}$. During the morning backtracking period, simple geometric analysis yields

$$d(E_{1,n}, \mathcal{T}_{k_S}(E_{2,n})) = \sec(\omega_{ID}). \quad (6)$$

It should be noted that this equation is well-defined, since during backtracking it always holds that $\omega_{ID} \neq 0$.

Hence, the condition for activating backtracking becomes

$$\sec(\omega_{ID}) \geq L_{EW} \Leftrightarrow L_{EW} \cos(\omega_{ID}) \leq 1. \quad (7)$$

An analogous condition applies symmetrically during the afternoon backtracking period.

To avoid shading, the tracker angle is corrected from the ideal value ω_{ID} by applying a backtracking correction angle ω_C^{BT} such that [14]

$$\cos(\omega_C^{BT}) = L_{EW} \cos(\omega_{ID}). \quad (8)$$

Accordingly, the resulting angle ω_{IDC} of the generator with respect to the horizontal during backtracking is given by

$$\omega_{IDC} = \omega_{ID} - \omega_C^{BT}. \quad (9)$$

This correction is the minimum required to prevent shading while minimizing energy losses due to deviation from the optimal angle. Therefore, the trackers are not rotated further than necessary, and under ideal conditions, the ground between rows remains completely shaded during backtracking periods, as illustrated in **Figure 3**.

Figure 3: Schematic representation of the backtracking configuration. Colours in the notation match the corresponding elements they refer to.

2.2 Unevenness effect on backtracking

An essential assumption in the geometric model introduced above is the flatness of the terrain, whereby all tracker axes are assumed to lie on the same horizontal plane. While this simplification facilitates simulation and analytical treatment, it does not accurately reflect the conditions of real-world utility-scale PV plants. In practice, field inspections conducted during backtracking periods consistently revealed the presence of illuminated strips of ground between adjacent tracker rows, as illustrated in **Figure 4**. This empirical observation contradicts the theoretical prediction of complete ground shading during backtracking, indicating that additional factors must be influencing the actual behavior.

Figure 4: Field observation during backtracking showing systematic presence of light strips between adjacent tracker rows.

One of the contributors to this discrepancy is terrain

unevenness, which introduces small but significant elevation differences between tracker rows. These vertical misalignments give rise to two possible shading scenarios. Focusing on the morning backtracking period, though the same reasoning applies in the afternoon, if a given tracker row $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ is situated at a slightly higher elevation than its preceding row $n - 1$, its shadow fails to reach the adjacent row, resulting in a light strip on the ground. Conversely, if row n is at a lower elevation than row $n - 1$, the shadow extends beyond the intended spacing, causing inter-row shading losses, the very outcome that backtracking algorithms are designed to avoid. These effects are illustrated schematically in **Figure 5**.

Figure 5: Schematic representation of the effects of terrain-induced elevation differences between tracker rows. The first generator row illustrates the appearance of light strips on the ground when the preceding row lies at a lower elevation. The second row depicts unintended shading (represented as a red segment) caused by a higher preceding row. The notation of each element is directly associated with its representative colour.

Interestingly, in actual PV plants, only the first of these scenarios, i.e. light strips between rows, was commonly observed. A plausible explanation is that shading between rows is undesirable not only due to its impact on energy yield but also because it generates hotspots that must be addressed during maintenance, and it is visually conspicuous. Consequently, it is hypothesized that the theoretical tracker positioning is deliberately adjusted in practice to prioritize the elimination of inter-row shading, even at the cost of reduced irradiance capture. This adjustment explains the systematic presence of ground illumination during backtracking periods, even on seemingly flat terrains.

3 APPROACH AND RESULTS

To validate the hypothesis proposed at the end of the previous section, SCADA data from the four PV plants under consideration were analyzed. These datasets included the angular position of each tracker, recorded as the empiric inclination angle ω_E with respect to the horizontal. To assess whether the angular position differs significantly across trackers within each PV plant, a pre-selection of trackers was performed based on data availability and quality. After this filtering, it was observed that the angular behavior of the selected trackers within each plant remained largely consistent over time. This observation supports the assumption that a single representative tracker per PV plant can reliably characterize the overall tracking behavior. Accordingly, the subsequent analysis focuses on one tracker per PV plant.

Table I summarizes the main characteristics of the analyzed PV plants, including their geographical location

and the normalized inter-row spacing L_{EW} of each configuration. The second Mexican plant corresponds to a separate parcel within the same facility as the first and is therefore labeled 1.2, while the original is labeled 1.1 for clarity.

Table I: Some relevant technical specifications of the studied PV plants.

PV Plant	Location	$L_{EW}/ []$
1.1	Mexico	3.00
1.2	Mexico	3.00
2	Chile	2.26
3	Chile	2.56
4	Spain	2.74

Figure 6 illustrates, for PV plant 1.1 located in Mexico, the evolution of the generator’s inclination angle throughout a full day, specifically on the spring equinox. The orange curve corresponds to the simulated tracker angle ω_{IDC} , while blue dots represent the experimental SCADA data ω_E . The difference between both values, shown as a dashed purple line (referenced to the right axis), reveals a sharp increase during backtracking intervals, highlighted with a white background. This confirms the deviation of real tracker behavior from the theoretical prediction specifically during those periods.

It should also be noted that the purple curve experiences a sudden change in trend at the end of the first daily backtracking period and at the beginning of the second. This behavior can be explained by the trackers reaching their mechanical saturation position, typically fixed around 55° . In the orange curve of **Figure 6**, this saturation is clearly visible as a flat region, reflecting the fact that, beyond this limit, the trackers can no longer follow the theoretical trajectory.

Figure 6: Comparison between simulated and measured tracker angles throughout the spring equinox day for PV plant 1.1, located in Mexico. The orange curve represents the theoretical inclination angle ω_{IDC} obtained from the ideal backtracking model, while the dark blue dots correspond to the experimental SCADA data ω_E . The dashed purple line, referenced to the right axis, quantifies the deviation between both values, which becomes particularly pronounced during backtracking intervals, highlighted with a white background. To account for this effect, a corrected simulation ω_{TA} was performed by introducing a reduced effective row-to-row distance \tilde{L}_{EW} . This correction, shown in dark yellow, results in a noticeable improvement, as reflected in the reduced discrepancy displayed in light blue, also, referenced to the right axis.

Figure 7 presents analogous results for the remaining

PV plants located in Spain, Chile, and the second parcel in Mexico (PV plant 1.2), focusing exclusively on the first backtracking interval of the same day. Owing to the symmetry of the tracker motion with respect to solar noon, the analysis of this initial interval is sufficient, since the behavior observed during the second backtracking period mirrors that of the first.

Figure 7: Simulated and measured tracking angles during the morning backtracking interval on the spring equinox for four PV plants. Each plot shows the original simulation ω_{IDC} (orange curve), the measured SCADA data ω_E (blue dots), and the initial discrepancy between them (dashed purple line, referenced to the right axis). The corrected simulated ω_{TA} using a reduced normalized spacing \tilde{L}_{EW} is shown in dark yellow, while the resulting new discrepancy with ω_E is plotted in light blue (also referenced to the right axis). The backtracking interval is highlighted with a white background, where angular deviations are more pronounced and the correction significantly improves agreement.

In response to these observations, the angular configuration of the trackers at the PV plants was not modified. Instead, a correction was introduced within the simulation algorithm to replicate the observed deviations. This correction consists of recalculating the backtracking angle ω_{IDC} by assuming a reduced normalized inter-row spacing \tilde{L}_{EW} in Equation (8), while preserving the actual physical configuration. In other words, a lower L_{EW} is used as an input to the backtracking algorithm, which forces a slightly smaller tracking angle, thereby generating light strips on the ground in the idealized model that mimic those observed in the field.

Focusing on the morning backtracking period, this correction accounts for terrain unevenness: if a row is slightly lower than its predecessor, the margin introduced by the modified angle allows it to remain illuminated, provided the elevation difference remains within acceptable bounds. Conversely, if the row is slightly higher than the preceding one, the light strip widens, leading to reduced irradiance capture, but without introducing shading and, thus, maintaining one of the fundamental objectives of backtracking.

It is also worth noting that outside the backtracking periods, the tracker angle is independent of L_{EW} , making this correction easily implementable in practice by simulating the tracking angles for an entire day with a modified L_{EW} . However, as shown in Equation (7), the limits of the backtracking period do depend on L_{EW} . In practice, this effect is not observed in the analyzed plants, since the saturation angle of the trackers is reached before the theoretical backtracking periods end (or begin, in the case of the afternoon backtracking intervals).

The same figures discussed in this section also include,

in dark yellow, the results of the simulation with the corrected angle ω_{TA} , obtained using \tilde{L}_{EW} . The light blue curve (again referenced to the right axis) represents the new discrepancy with respect to the measured values ω_E , which is now reduced by several orders of magnitude compared to the original simulation.

Finally, the relative annual variation $\Delta(\text{TIG}_A)$ in tracking irradiation gain (TIG) between the ideal and corrected configurations is computed as

$$\Delta(\text{TIG}_A) = \frac{\text{TIG}_A(\omega_{IDC}) - \text{TIG}_A(\omega_{TA})}{\text{TIG}_A(\omega_{IDC})} \cdot 100, \quad (10)$$

where the explicit dependence of TIG on the tracking angle used in the simulation has been indicated in brackets. Moreover, to reflect the annual nature of the analysis, the temporal subscript T previously used is replaced by A . It should be noted that the simulation results obtained with SISIFO are computed using a Typical Meteorological Year (TMY) as input. Furthermore, the applied correction is conceptually analogous to introducing an artificial East–West slope on the terrain, thereby modifying the effective geometry of the PV plant [10]. This scenario can be easily simulated in SISIFO, which natively supports simulations on sloped terrain, representing a major improvement over most existing PV simulation tools. The resulting values of $\Delta(\text{TIG}_A)$ for each PV plant are summarized in **Table II**, together with the corresponding normalized spacing \tilde{L}_{EW} used in the corrected simulations.

Table II: Normalized inter-row spacing \tilde{L}_{EW} and relative annual tracking irradiation gain variation $\Delta(\text{TIG}_A)$ for the analyzed PV plants.

PV Plant	$\tilde{L}_{EW} / []$	$\Delta(\text{TIG}_A) / [\%]$
1.1	2.50	7.3
1.2	2.50	7.3
2	1.96	9.4
3	2.24	9.2
4	2.16	7.8

4 CONCLUSIONS

The widespread overestimation of energy production in PV simulations can be partly attributed to an overvaluation of the tracking irradiation gain. Experimental data from four PV plants across different countries show that systematic angle corrections are applied in the field to prevent mutual shading caused by terrain unevenness. A reverse-engineering approach, based on considering a reduced inter-row spacing, reveals that these corrections lead to TIG values 7–10% lower than theoretical estimates. This results in an average annual energy yield overestimation of about 3%, roughly half of the typical discrepancy between simulated and actual performance [10].

5 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors express their sincere appreciation for the financial support provided through the project PVOP, funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

The authors are also grateful to EU PVSEC for the opportunity to present their work at the 2025 edition held in Bilbao, Spain. Special thanks go to the research staff at the Instituto de Energía Solar of the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid for their valuable contributions.

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